

LINGUISTIC CHARACTERISTICS OF OIKONIM AND HYDRONYMS IN THE GERMAN LANGUAGE

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Annotation.

This article analyzes the linguistic and cultural features of onyms and hydronyms in German and Uzbek languages. In this, it is explained that toponyms, names and hydronyms represent the culture, customs and traditions of the inhabitants of each region. The importance of the traditions and customs of the German peoples in the naming of places is mentioned.

Key words.

relationship between the concepts of language and culture, linguistic culture, synonyms and hydronyms in the German language, Berlin, Hamburg, Köln, Donau, Rhein,

When we consider the issue of "Language and culture" in linguistics, we can see that the priority rightfully belongs to the German linguist Wilhelm von Humboldt. It is he who is recognized by linguists around the world as the founder of theoretical linguistics. He was the first to put forward the idea of a close relationship between language and thought and their inseparable interaction in any human life. W. von Humboldt in his writings "language is, as it were, the external manifestation of the soul of the people: the language of the people is its soul, and the soul of the people is its language, and it is difficult to imagine the same thing" [Humboldt 2000: 68].

The problem of the relationship between language, thought and culture has been a concern of philologists, philosophers and cultural scientists for many years. Some scholars have debated the "primacy" and function of each component of this well-known triad. From the diachronic point of view, L. Weisgerber [Weissgerber 2004], who introduced the concept of "linguistic picture of the world" with this issue, L. Wittgenstein put forward the idea that "my language defines the limits", the limits of my world" [Wittgenstein 2005], E. Sapir (linguistic relativity theory)

[Sapir 1993] and B. Whorf (linguistic determinism theory) [Whorf 2003]. In the works of the Russian philologist A.A. Potebnya von Humboldt's ideas were continued in his materials on Slavic languages and cultures (see [Potebnya 1999]).

Local linguist S.G. In his review article entitled "Cultural Linguistics, Language and National Mentality", Shafikov examines the main concepts of linguoculturology and the interrelationship between culture, language and national mentality: "Culture is a very complex concept, and it is impossible to talk about the uniqueness of this phenomenon or the close connection between them. language; Linguistic culture using the concept of "linguistic culture" does not take this into account; Just as language unites people of different cultures, social culture can unite people speaking different languages" [Shafikov 2013].

Linguist scientist V.V. Vorobyov understands linguoculturology as "a complex scientific discipline that studies the practical relationship and interaction of culture and language and reflects this process as an integral structure of units in the unity of linguistic and extralinguistic (cultural) content" [Vorobyev 1996: 4.]. Linguistic culture, which is the successor of linguistic and cultural studies, means "a new way of thinking, a new system of cultural values fully and objectively put forward by the modern life of society. Interpretation of facts and events and information about various spheres of the country's cultural life. Changes in people's lives, new priorities guidance requires effective, complete, truthful information" [Vorobyev 2006: 35].

A toponymic dictionary, which explicitly or implicitly includes socio-historical or geographical phenomena, shows the result of a conscious naming process, which also helps to create an ethno-linguistic picture of the world. Referring to the classification of toponyms proposed by N.V. Podolskaya [Podolskaya 1978], in this study we use the terms "oykonym" - the name of a city and "hydronym" - the name of a water body. Check out some of the five largest German cities and the names of important bodies of water - German Hydronyms.

BERLIN/BERLIN

The name of the capital of Germany, Berlin, appears for the first time in documents of the 13th century and, according to the most likely version, comes from the Old Slavic term birl/berl - "swamp, swamp" [Toponomic dictionary] 2005: 74]. Interestingly, Germans use the expression einen Koffer in Berlin haben - lit. To have a suitcase in Berlin means "to have a reason to return to Berlin, to be connected with Berlin". rose to fame thanks to the pop song R.M. Siegel's "Ich hab' noch einen Koffer in Berlin" performed by the famous Marlene Dietrich [Küpper 1997: 442].

HAMBURG/HAMBURG

The following proverb unites two German cities: Hamburg ist das Tor zur Welt, aber Bremen hat den Schlüssel dazu or its variant Hamburg ist das Tor zum Himmel, aber Bremen hat den Schlüssel dazu - lit. "Hamburg is the gateway to the world (heaven), but Bremen has the key." In this story, Hamburg's coat of arms depicts a gate, and Bremen's coat of arms shows the key of Peter the Apostle, the patron saint of Bremen Cathedral. The Pospel etymology of the Hamburg toponym is revealed as follows: "... a German city-place, mentioned as Hammaburg in 715; This name appears in the Middle and High German period. - "bay, river bend", burg - "fortified city", i.e. "the city by the river bay" [Toponomic dictionary 2005: 95]. Today, "Hamburg ist eine Hafenstadt" is a port city.

KOLN/KÖLN

The appearance of the Cologne icon is directly related to the history of the development of Germany. The origin of this name is known: "it comes from the Latin colonia (Kolonie) - the Roman name of the colony Claudia Ara Agrippinensium" [Electronic resource [http s: // de.wiktionary.org/wiki/Köln](http://de.wiktionary.org/wiki/Köln)]. it is said: a Roman camp was founded in AD 50. It received the status of a Roman colony and was named Colonia Agrippinensis in honor of Agrippina, the wife of the Roman emperor Julius Caesar, who was born in this military camp. appeared" [Toponymic Dictionary 2005: 139]. Thus, the city of Cologne was named in memory of the birth of the emperor's wife in the Roman colony.

HYDRONYMS

RHEIN/DER RHEIN

The famous Rhine River, which flows into the North Sea, sung by many poets, appears more than any other in folk songs, proverbs and sayings. The name of the river was first recorded in the sources of the IV century BC: "... the name is reconstructed from the Indo-European base reinos -" river, stream "; probably from Celtic languages, here Gaulish renos, rhenus - "flowing water, river" [Toponomic dictionary 2005: 218]. In this case, the name of the river appeared as a natural phenomenon in the life of the people of ancient Germany: they called the river "flowing water", amazed by its width and speed. The conceptual image of the world becomes a linguistic image: the water resource that supplies people with water and food receives a characteristic designation.

Of the many different characteristics that apply to candidacy, only socio-historical conditions, the general level of development of the ethno-society ultimately determine the choice of one or another characteristic. Hydronyms are able to reflect not the environment in which they appeared, but the attitude of

society to this environment. Not only great poets wrote songs and poems about the Rhine (F. Schiller, F. Liszt, G. Heine ("Germany - a winter's tale", "Rhine. Lorelei"). Germans affectionately call this river Vater Rhine. (Father Rhine) .

The vastness and beauty of the Rhine has given rise to many sayings:

Rheinleute, Weinleute - people on the banks of the Rhine have long been engaged in viticulture and winemaking [Maltseva 2001: 13].

Particularly noteworthy are the lines from popular German songs that refer to this beautiful river:

"Has Reben been brought? ... Vom Rhein den Wein!" (Beginn eines Rheinweinliedes).

"Grüß' mir das blonde Kind vom Rhein und sag' ich käme wieder" (aus einem rheinischen Heimatlied).

"Die Frau vom Vater Rhein ist die Frau Mosel, drei Kinder heißen Neckar, Saar und Main. Und dieser so behremung Rhein-Familie, verdanken wir den herrlich goldnen Wein" (deutsches Rheinwein-Lied).

"Trinkst du mal Wein vom Rhein, gib' acht auf den Jahrgang; küßt du ein Mägdelein, gib' acht auf den Jahrgang (Rheinweinlied) [Electronic resource [http s://de.wiktionary .org/wiki/Rhein](http://de.wiktionary.org/wiki/Rhein)].

DUNE/DIE DONAU

The origin and use of the name of another famous river - the Danube - is interesting. The Danube, which remains the largest river in foreign Europe, flows through nine countries, including Germany. No wonder many poets sing about the beauty of this river. The name of the river was first mentioned by the ancient Greek author Hesiod in the 7th century BC. as Istres (Istros); a Thracian name from an Indo-European stem meaning "to flow, to move" and referring to the lower course of a river. At the same time, the upper and middle parts of the course are referred to in ancient Roman sources as Danubian (1st century BC).

registered under the name As the Celts moved east, the name replaced the Thracian Istres. The form Danuv indicates that this hydronym is related to the Iranian word danu - "river". The current name of the Danube River is mentioned in chronicles since the 10th century [Toponomic dictionary 2005: 112].

The examples discussed above show how the etymology of German toponyms is related to extralinguistic, including geographical and political factors. The name of a town or river is not only distinctive and valuable, but together with various appellatives and often with toponyms forms a new collective expression used in modern German. The wisdom of the people, their involvement in winemaking and military affairs, and their love for mother nature find expression in proverbs and

sayings that describe the world as the Germans perceive it. In this way, the toponyms in the German language also represent the historical culture of the German people. The people are trying to pass these names on to the next generation.

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